

This document forms section ten of the University of Bath's Responsible Research Assessment Guidance and should be read alongside [the full guidance](#). You can find more information on the [RRA webpage](#).

10. Scenarios of responsible research assessment in practice

The following scenarios provide examples of assessment practices that do and do not comply with our principles for responsible research assessment.

Scenario 1: allocating prizes and awards.

Flo is assessing research outputs for an award for research excellence. One of the research outputs is from a field very far from their own and due to this, as well as time pressures, Flo resorts to finding the journal impact factor and number of citations to help them understand the quality of the paper.

Question: Is this approach consistent with our RRA principles?

No

- Expert judgement and peer review is central to the responsible assessment approach at Bath.
- Reliable and responsible metrics can be used to support, but never replace, expert judgement.
- Journal impact factors and raw citation counts are not considered a reliable metric for quality.
- In this instance, the following actions could have improved the assessment:
 - The assessment process could have asked individuals to outline their contribution, the quality of the content including novelty and robustness of design, and its impact, visibility and reach in the field. This would help assessors in adjacent fields to access contextual information that supports their expert judgement.
 - Ensuring a panel of assessors would help ensure that disciplinary biases or knowledge gaps are minimised in the assessment process.
 - In the absence of the above, Flo could have requested expert peer review from someone closer to the research area.

Scenario 2: assessing job applications

Ali advertised a Lecturer role. When creating the role in Stonefish, Ali used one of the four questions to ask applicants: “Please describe your best 3 research outputs. Explain the contribution you made to each output, the quality of the research and its design, and the visibility, reach, influence, or impact of these outputs.”

Question: Is this consistent with our RRA principles?

Yes

Ali has encouraged the candidate to present evidence against the three core facets of research quality for research outputs (1 - contribution, 2 - quality of content, and 3 - impact, influence, visibility and reach).

By asking the question explicitly in this way, Ali has ensured the panel have the best possible chance of accessing meaningful evidence to assess against the criteria.

The question focusses on the quality of the candidate’s outputs not the number of outputs.

Ali would need to include a maximum word count for this question to ensure that the shortlisting process is as manageable as possible.

Scenario 3: assessing job applications.

Chandrika advertised for a Lecturer role. When creating the role in Stonefish, Chandrika used one of the four questions to ask applicants: "Please describe your contribution to research and the generation of knowledge and list the 3 research outputs that you would like to put forward to be reviewed."

Question: Is this consistent with our RRA principles

Yes - partially

Asking the candidate to nominate their top three research outputs focuses on quality over quantity and is more likely to reflect the research identity of the individual than randomly selecting outputs from their publication list to review.

But!

Clarity: 'Contributions to research' may not be universally understood. It might help to be transparent with the candidates what will be considered (e.g. outputs, research grants, innovation/ enterprise, impact, research supervision or otherwise).

Format: If Chandrika was expecting a large number of applications, it would be unrealistic for the panel to review 3 outputs per candidate. This question may be better placed further along the recruitment process when there is a smaller pool of shortlisted candidates. Proposing a word limit would also ensure assessment is manageable for assessors.

The question could be rephrased: "Please describe your contribution to research and the generation of knowledge (including X, Y, and Z) in 300 words. Please also list 3 research outputs that you would like to be reviewed by the panel if you are selected for interview. Please note they will not be reviewed at shortlisting, so consider whether you would also like to summarise any of these contributions in your 300 word statement. "

For more information read [the full guidance](#) or visit the [RRA webpage](#).